

ECHOLOT Insights #01

The ECHOLOT project marks an important milestone with the release of its first newsletter, coinciding with its six-month anniversary. Despite its short duration, the project has already made significant progress, with various activities, collaborations, events attended and developments underway. This inaugural edition provides an overview of these achievements and sets the scene for the future.

MILESTONES

**The ECHOLOT website
is available!**

Visit the ECHOLOT website

We are proud to present the ECHOLOT website. This important milestone is packed with content and covers all aspects of the project, explaining what makes ECHOLOT such a special and exciting initiative.

- ◆ Who we are.
- ◆ Our objectives and impact.
- ◆ Our Foundation.
- ◆ Our design approach.
- ◆ All about the five case studies in which the ECHOLOT system will be tested and validated.
- ◆ The resources and news we will produce.
- ◆ A dedicated page for the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) developed by [ECHOES](#).

Visit the site and discover how ECHOLOT will enable the the creation, provision and reuse of high-quality, semantically rich, interoperable cultural data.

Visit the ECHOLOT
website

INSIDE ECHOLOT

ECHOLOT kicks off with two consortium meetings

The ECHOLOT consortium held **two meetings in the first two months** of its existence, demonstrating a strong commitment to shaping the future of cultural heritage data in Europe.

The **official kick-off meeting** of the ECHOLOT project took place **online on 14 and 15 January**. It provided an excellent opportunity to introduce the consortium partners, allocate tasks and draw up the project's roadmap for the next 36 months.

The **second meeting** of the consortium **was held in Bilbao, Spain, from 9 to 11 March**. Hosted by the University of the Basque Country, the meeting had two main objectives. Firstly, it was a natural follow-up to the online kick-off meeting. Secondly, the meeting was conceived as a requirements-gathering workshop.

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EVENTS & OUTREACH

ECHOLOT makes its debut at the ECHOES EU second annual event

From 16 to 20 March, [ECHOES](#), the organisation responsible for the [European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage](#) (ECCCH) platform, held its [Second Annual Event](#) in Poznań, Poland. **ECHOLOT** was thrilled to have the opportunity to **participate actively** over the five days and **make its debut at an international event** alongside its sister projects. ECHOLOT was represented by Lozana Rossenova from [TIB](#), the project coordinator.

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MediaWiki Users and Developers Conference Spring 2026

10th anniversary of Transformation Digital Art

The [MediaWiki Users and Developers Conference Spring 2026](#) took place from 25 to 27 March in Salt Lake City, Utah, USA.

On the first day of the conference, ECHOLOT partners from Professional Wiki and KM-A Knowledge Management gave a presentation introducing NeoWiki, an open-source structured data system baked by the ECHOLOT project.

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From 26 to 27 March, LI-MA – Living Media Art hosted in Amsterdam the 10th anniversary of [Transformation Digital Art \(TDA\)](#), the annual international symposium dedicated to the preservation of digital art.

On the second day, Lozana Rossenova, the ECHOLOT project coordinator from [TIB](#), presented the project at a panel titled ‘Connecting Archives, Collections and Data’.

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ECHOLOT attends Art History Loves Wiki 2026

The Art History Loves Wiki 2026 conference, co-organised by the [KuWiki community](#), took place at the [Museum Schnütgen](#) in Cologne from 27 to 29 March. The communities came together to discuss the impact, challenges and benefits of working with cultural knowledge and data on platforms such as Wikipedia, Wikimedia Commons and Wikidata. The ECHOLOT presentation, titled ‘Optimierte Linked Open Data Tools für das kulturelle Erbe in Europa’, and delivered by the project’s coordinator

ECHOLOT participates at the ‘Engineering Truth’ online event

On 15 May, the [ECHOES of Memory](#) project hosted an online synergy event titled [‘Engineering Truth: AI Governance, Data Safety, and the Architecture of Trust’](#). Designed as both a networking opportunity and a first step towards identifying future collaboration opportunities, the event provided a space for cross-project dialogue. The ECHOLOT team presented some of the challenges we are currently facing and the strategies we are developing when designing the AI-

Lozana Rossenova from [TIB](#), was a perfect fit for the discussions.

supported workflows in the ECHOLOT enrichment system.

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ECHOLOT at Digital Heritage Summit 2026

The [Digital Heritage Summit 2026](#) took place from 25 to 29 May in Limassol, Cyprus, bringing together world-renowned experts, institutions, and industry leaders. ECHOLOT was, of course, present at the Summit. Rony Vissers from [Meemoo](#), Flemish Institute for Archives, a member of our consortium, represented ECHOLOT at the event in Limassol.

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Oulu Löyly Open culture think & do fest

ECHOLOT at the the AI-Bridges Symposium

The [AI-BRIDGES symposium](#) took place at the Senate House, [University of London](#), on 29 May, under the theme ‘Bridging Institutions, Open Knowledge, and AI’. ECHOLOT was represented by its coordinator from [TIB](#), who joined an expert panel, and by partners from [UPV/EHU](#) and [Wikimedia Sverige](#), who joined roundtables held at the end of the symposium.

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ECHOLOT participates at the GOBLIN Hackathon

[AvoingLAM](#) organised the ‘[Oulu Löyly](#)’ event from 8 to 10 June as part of the ‘Oulu 2026 – European Capital of Culture’ programme.

Jouni Tuominen, from the [University of Helsinki](#), represented ECHOLOT at the Open Culture Marketplace, a one-day event within the workshop open to everyone, with a roll-up banner and a stand.

The [GOBLIN Hackathon on Metadata and Provenance for Knowledge Graphs](#) took place from 8 to 9 June in Oviedo, Spain.

Its main theme was to improve the quality, context and traceability of knowledge graphs. As it is closely linked to ECHOLOT, David Lindemann, from [EHU](#) represented the project.

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SYNERGIES & COLLABORATION

ECHOES Sister projects join forces to celebrate World Heritage Day 2026

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World Heritage Day 2026 took place on 18 April. This day reminds us that **protecting cultural heritage is not just about preserving the past**; it’s also about finding new ways to understand, experience and care for it. This is precisely the area in which the sister projects of the European

Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage ([ECCCH](#)), guided by [ECHOES](#), are making their contribution.

To celebrate World Heritage Day 2026, ECHOES has created a **carousel highlighting how the projects come together** across four connected areas, with input from all sister projects.

[Discover more](#)

ECHOLOT Survey:
Tell us how you use MediaWiki
outside of Wikimedia projects

Take part in the ECHOLOT survey

Take part in our survey and help us **understand how you use MediaWiki outside of Wikimedia projects!**

At ECHOLOT, we are trying to learn more about how [MediaWiki](#) is used outside of the original projects of the [Wikimedia Foundation](#), such as Wikipedia, Wikibooks, Wiktionary, Wikiquote, Wikimedia Commons, Wikisource, Wikiversity, Wikispecies, Wikidata and Wikifunctions. MediaWiki is the open-source software that powers these projects, but it is also used for many other purposes. Although we focus particularly on the GLAM sector (galleries, libraries, archives and museums), we also welcome responses from other sectors, such as private or public organisations, as well as from the fields of research and education.

Deadline: 30 June.

[ECHOLOT survey](#)

ECHOLOT Project

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